

Original Research Article

Saudi Women's Empowerment to Enhance their Engagement in the Local Societal Institutions

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Abstract

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This study aimed at identifying ways to empower the Saudi women to enhance their engagement in the local community institutions, and reveal their empowerment degree, as well as the degree of their enhancement in such institutions. It further aimed to identify how to enhance the participation of the Saudi women in the local societal institutions. The study population comprised all the Saudi women who are working in the community institutions in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and a sample of (60) Saudi women were randomly chosen. To achieve the study objectives, the researchers constructed a questionnaire based on the pertinent theoretical literature and previous studies. The questionnaire validity was verified through presenting to arbiters, while the reliability coefficient was extracted through Cronbach Alpha equation. The results showed that all Chi-square values for all the items of the first domain "Empowerment of women" were statistically significant at (0.05) level and that the empowerment degree was medium. They also showed that all Chi-square values for all the items of the second domain "Engagement of the Saudi women in the community institutions" were statistically significant at (0.05) level and the engagement degree was medium. Finally, the results showed that all Chi-square values for all the items of the third domain "Enhancement of the Saudi women's engagement in the local community institutions" were statistically significant at (0.05) level and the enhancement degree was medium too.

Keywords: Empowerment, Saudi women, Societal institutions, Women's empowerment

INTRODUCTION

Women have a great role in the community development and progress, just like men. Their vital role cannot be overlooked in raising the generations and preparing them to be source of continuity and development of the states and civilizations. This leads to the importance of preparing and empowering the women in a conscience and real manner to be the partners of men in all life aspects. No one can belittle the significance of the role of women in the community. They realize this role and work toward commitment to their duties, practice of their rights and influence in the upgrading and development of their countries. Therefore, women should be engaged in the

development plans and processes through proper education and training, to face the cultural, social and economic challenges of the age (Al-Hariri, 2003).

Since women constitute half the community and have its productive energy, they are part of the development process too. The progress and development of any community became tightly connected to the degree of the women's progress and engagement in the social development and other fields (Al-Najjar, 2009). In the past, the Saudi women were not overlooked since the inception of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. They had an active role in the Saudi community renaissance, and

were an active partner in the development process through their participation in both the public and private sectors. This was due to the strong determination and perseverance that the Saudi women possess, and the Saudi government awareness of their participation in the comprehensive development process. Their participation dates back to the era of late/King Abdel Aziz (may Allah bestow mercy on his soul), when women had a clear role in education through Katateeb (the then traditional schools) for females, both the independent and public (volunteer female teachers). Girls were taught reading, writing and Holy Quran in these Katateeb (Al-Yazidi, 2009).

Recently, there is a noticeable attention of the human issues and development in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. In this regard, many higher resolutions were passed in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia ruling in the importance of engaging the Saudi women in the development and developmental participation in the different social, economic and political and other institutions. These resolutions underline the importance of engaging the women in the development process through ruling out discrimination between men and women, and treating them as strategic partners of the men in the Saudi community. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as a member in the UNO, worked on assuring the equality between the two genders and enabling the women. Adopting their participation rate in the national parliamentary seats by 2015 is a clear indicator in this concern, which was in line with the developmental goals of the third millennium that were approved by the member states of the UNO (UN, 2008). This was consistent with Beijing Conference Agreement . which emphasized the women's participation in the political, economic and social public life, to achieve social justice and societal development.

Therefore, the interest in women and their participation in the development of their community became an important issue at both the domestic and foreign levels, because they are part of the human wealth and should be empowered and supported to be able to take decisions and participate in the development process (Abu Al-Naser, 2007). The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia was pioneer in this field, namely the care, empowerment and support of the women and encouraging them to participate in the community institutions. An example is King Abdul Aziz Charitable Society for women, which was established in Muharram 1422 AH, corr. to 26 March 2001 AD, in Skaka area, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which aims at supporting the women. Among the services provided to the women are: taking care of the talented students and the women's affairs; study of the related phenomena; work toward raising their level, culturally and socially; reviving the folklore related to the women; management of the social aids fund of the women; holding specialized training centers to rehabilitate the women with different crafts and skills; looking after the widows and divorced women of

the needy families, and many other services (Abdel, 2009).

Princess Sara Bint Abdullah Award was launched to support the women through the Productive Family Program, which contributes to the women's engagement in the economic and social development through small projects (Oweis, 2011). Princess Sara provided full support to prepare the training programs that enable and qualify the Saudi women with the required technical, marketing and administrative skills, to be an active participant in the economic and social sectors (Issa, 2004). The basic ruling system in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia included the issuance of the Royal Decree No. (90/A) dated 27/8/1412 AH. The seventeenth article of the system stipulated the equality between men and women in the economic and social areas. Accordingly, the women's economic and social roles were enhanced through encouragement and support in the Kingdom. Thereby, the Saudi women were recognized as an active element in the community by eliminating the discrimination features against them, and adopting mechanisms that help them to become self-reliant. This was based on the higher Royal Decree No. (651) on 8/6/1421 AH that approved sending the Saudi women abroad on scholarships to qualify them in majors that are not included in the domestic Saudi universities (Al-Maizer, 2015). However, the Saudi women took part in the international forums to sign international agreements that work toward qualifying and empowerment of women in the different economic, social, public and private sectors area. The Decree aimed at the empowerment and education of the women to become participants in the Saudi community development since the inception of the Kingdom, through the national development plans to enhance the status of women by broadening the available chances to them in education and training, and through finding job opportunities, as indicated in the first five-year development document (1390-1395 AH) (Central Planning Authority, 1390). This interest also continued in the second five-year plan (1395-1400) that emphasized the women's empowerment through education and training to become effective members in the community (Al-Maizer, 2015).

It is clear that leaderships of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia were pioneers in taking care of women in the fields of qualification, education and empowerment, to become effective actors in the community development as fundamental partners with men, and through ruling out all types of discrimination, based on the laws and legislations that the Kingdom enacted during the previous and current eras. They further worked to provide material and moral support to women, and join and take part in all the international forums that are interested in qualifying and enabling the women in their communities (Al—Suhaimi, 2013). emphasized in her study that the Saudi state paid wide attention to the women. It adopted their right in education, work, social and health care, right to

own property, business management, occupying leading positions, inter alia. In addition, it supported their role in the various areas, in spite of the challenges in the Saudi cultural and social heritage.

Women's empowerment is the process through which they are able to identify their situations realistically, acquire skills and experiences, and develop their abilities through self-reliance (Al-Shinnawi, 2006).

Al-Sa'ati and Samia (2003) found that women's empowerment works to improve their status as one of the sustainable development objectives, achieving equality and fairness between men and women. In addition, the women will be engaged in decision-making process at all social and political and other levels, because empowerment aims at upgrading and improving the women's skills and giving them opportunities to make use of the resources to prove their abilities. The women's social engagement degree relies on the services degree the community provides to them and helps them perform these roles, which are represented in the social work facilities, training centers, guidance and counseling offices, health care centers, such as the hospitals, and libraries and sports clubs (UNIFEM 2004). There was a worldwide trend toward the attention of the women's status and enabling them to share in all the different life aspects, since the International Women Decade (1975-1985) (UN, 2000). It aims to enable the women control their lives and take the proper decisions; and help them to employ the strength they discovered in their personalities through work with others, to generate a positive change and reach self-dependence. In this concern, empowerment comes from the inside of the individual, and the women became more participating in the life activities and social institutions by self-awareness after enabling them to serve the community (Al-Jundi and Nadia, 2001).

Nonetheless, we find that the woman (herself) creates the most prominent obstacles that are related to her directly, which prevent her reach the senior and leading positions. Many of the working women prefer the routine works, part-time jobs and less advanced and developed occupational tracks; because this facilitates them to combine between their occupational and home requirements. This is particularly true in the rarity of social institutions such as nurseries, clubs and even public parks, which, in turn, increases the burden on the working women, and decreases their ambition and aspiration to occupy leading positions. This is further emphasized by the human capital theory in terms of the use of "Self-Selection" concept, to interpret the differences of the representation rates of men and women in certain positions; and, subsequently, emergence of a labor market with discrimination between the two genders (Haddad, 2004). The women's empowerment degree, at the social level, could be measured by indicators, such as participation in the social work, their numbers in the decision-taking centers

pro rata with the total number, and number of the official and nonofficial social institutions in which they take part (Al-Balawi and Dhaif, 2018). Empowerment is deemed as a vehicle that liberates the human from restrictions, encourages, motivates and rewards him/her to practice the spirit of initiation and creativity (Farah, 2007). It is further deemed as partaking process in the community service through its social institutions, and is one of the great interests of the women, through which they attempt to achieve integration of their knowledge, skills and values. Their engagement in these institutions works toward improving and increasing their social performance. Thus, women are one of the pillars of the basic development of the society. Social institutions always seek benefits from the women's capabilities by transferring the community service into a profession to them, which women always seek to achieve. Women are able to share in the social events and activities and decision-making, which is one of the significant bases that the women's empowerment relies on. Empowerment, as one of the social work elements, focuses on raising awareness of the women and improving their abilities like those of men (Al-Haqeel, 2011). As a result of the accelerating developments in the world, which created changes in many of the individuals' roles in the communities, a change also occurred in the role of women. Many fields became available for women in which they can take part and contribute to the fulfillment of the community goals where they live; which require qualification, empowerment and knowledge of dealing with the technology of the age. There are many works that are available for the Saudi women to practice through computer, for example but not limited to: fashion design, trade, and scientific or health communication with various authorities and centers (Faraj, 2013).

The human is a basic component of the development process, and is the target of development. Success of this process is subject to participation, proper preparation, qualification and empowerment of the human to it. Women have a very important role in the development process as they are one of the production and services powers, and are able to create change in the communities through participation in the their institutions.

Empowerment is one of the important social concepts in the social development process, because it means the group cooperative work for the interest of parties or groups in the community that are in need for qualification, training and gaining different skills to overcome the obstacles they face. Empowerment is also an important concept in the women's progress in the community and is linked to them, because it helps them take decisions and understand and claim their rights (Zachariah, 2013). works to increase participation; liberates them from constrains; encourages and motivates them to practice the spirit of initiative and creativity (Hmoud, 1997).

Al-Khaldi (2013) and expresses their participation

effectiveness in decision making and implementation (Al-Baghdadi, 2013). Empowerment was, and is still, along with the societal institutions, two sides of the same coin, namely community service, due to their connectedness to achieving the societal justice among the individuals, emphasis on their civil rights, and importance of change that the individuals generate to their community through empowerment. The community institutions always achieve positive results in the community service (Al-Samalouti, 2007).

The women's empowerment is found in many domains as follows:

-Cognitive domain: such as acquiring self-learning skills, computer use skills, development of the logical thought in problem-solving.

-Social domain: through engagement in the societal development at both the local and national levels; understanding their rights and duties; and practicing their civil rights freely.

-Psychological domain: enabling the women to get rid of the inferior outlook to "themselves" that they are less than others, assuring their ability to help and serve others to improve their living conditions.

-Economic domain: encouraging the women to engage in new societal professions, training them to possess project management skills to improve the income, and rooting the principle of equality and justice with men in job opportunities.

-Rights and legislations domain: awareness of the women on their rights and social status.

-Environment and health domain: through their awareness of the principles of public health and family counseling (Sa'adallah, 2009).

There are obstacles and challenges that hinder the empowerment of the Arab women as seen by (Jaleeli, 2009) as follows: hard economic and political conditions; scarcity of the financial resources; lack of the women's development, awareness and training programs; overlap of the social, cultural and economic factors; and limited abilities and equipments that help in training and empowerment.

The ninth development plan in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia included ensuring the empowerment of the Saudi women to engage in the socioeconomic development through their participation in the developmental activities and the state institutions, such as Shura Council, municipal councils and many community professional institutions. Thereby, they became active elements in the social economic and political engagement. The rate of the Saudi women in the Saudi community members is

48% of the total population. The Kingdom placed attention to the women as a part of its comprehensive development, and enacted many laws that ensure the women's rights, participation, empowerment and support as main partners of men in the Saudi community. These procedures were based on its belief in the women's abilities in the development and progress of the Saudi community in all sectors. Attention was paid to empowering and supporting them both locally and internationally, as the Kingdom took part in many international conventions that support the women's empowerment. Truly, the Saudi women achieved a lot at the political, social, economic, health and other fields as well.

The Study Problem

Women are most often seen as having less participation than men in many development aspects, which is attributed to exclusion from decision-taking circles and inequality between the two genders. This, in turn, led to the women's poor partaking in labor, as they constitute only 16.7% of the total labor force, and limited participation in the labor market . although reality requires their participation in the socioeconomic development and their existence in the labor market. In this concern, the women's participation degree in the labor market depends on many factors, such as: female population in the community, educational and training policies, and social habits and traditions (Jaleeli, 2009). The Saudi women in the past (1330-1380 AH) lived under the shade of habits and traditions that made them lose many rights. Many prohibitions were imposed on them due to the authority of the family, male domination, the community culture that deprives the women of their rights, and discriminations between men and women. Their responsibilities were limited to caring for home and children, and certain professions such as frond manufacturing, embroidery, sewing and sheep herding (Saeed, 2002). There was inequality between men and women in fundamental life economic and political domains in terms of engagement and decision-taking . Women's participation was, and is still, largely unframed in many communities, which lessened their engagement in all the economic and social aspects, because their engagement in the community development has no material return or legal value. Social, economical, political and other developments took place in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in which the women had a considerable share, such as sublime Royal Orders, legal and human rights legislations, and support and care of the Saudi women at the different material and logistic levels. These developments led to the Saudi women's engagement in the comprehensive development process. They proved their existence on the political, economic and social map, and are still seeking stronger roles to partake in the

comprehensive development process at all levels, and at the social sector level in particular, because this sector largely and truly represents them as mothers, wives and teachers. They can be effectively influential in the social development in a more powerful manner, whether or not they are working, through empowerment, training and increasing their strengths, experiences, and motivation, to become more participating and able to take decisions to take part in the social development process through the social institutions. Accordingly, the study attempts to answer the following main question:

What are the ways to empower the Saudi women to enhance their participation in the local community institutions?

The following sub-questions stem from the main question:

- 1- What is the degree of Saudi women's empowerment?
- 2- What is the degree of the Saudi women's engagement in the local community institutions?
- 3- How to enhance the Saudi women's engagement in the local community institutions?

Purpose of the Study

The study aimed at identifying the following:

- 1- Ways to empower the Saudi women to enhance their engagement in the local societal institutions
- 2- Empowerment degree of the Saudi women.
- 3- Engagement degree of the Saudi women in the local societal institutions.
- 4- Ways to enhance the Saudi women's participation in the local societal institutions.

Significance of the Study

The significance of the study stems from the importance of the subjects it tackles, as it seeks to achieve the following:

- Identifying the optimal ways to empower the Saudi women, to enhance their participation in the community institutions, and become a part of the comprehensive development.
- Revealing the current empowerment degree of the Saudi women to proceed further in the empowerment process in the right place.
- Disclosing their actual participation degree at the present time in the community institutions and the best ways to enhance this participation. This will contribute to providing the decision makers and authorities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia with enhancement of the Saudi women's role, in a scientific and thoughtful way, based on the study results.
- Providing the library actual, scientific data about the duration and date of the study as a historical archive that

- helps in comparisons and measuring the role of women in the local community development.

Study Limits

The study was limited by the following determinants:

- **Human limits:** the study is limited to the Saudi women only.
- **Spatial limits:** the local community in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
- **Temporal limits:** the current 2020/2021 year.

Terminology

Empowerment (idiomatically): helping the individuals in defining the problem and planning for change, assisting them to use their strengths, abilities and efficiencies to be an important factor for solving their problems, to achieve empowerment, which is engaging through discovery of the individuals' strengths in their environment and utilizing them accordingly (Al-Naimat, 2010).

Women's Empowerment: building process through which the women become able to organize their affairs, rely on themselves, and manage their life affairs. It is a great internal self-confidence and ability to overcome the external challenges of the (Al-Yousef, 2009). Furthermore, it is the increase of the women's ability in taking strategic decisions for their lives in a certain context after their poor abilities before empowerment (Al-Sorouji, 2011).

The researchers defined the women's empowerment (procedurally) as an increase of the women's abilities and awareness by providing more opportunities to obtain the required knowledge, skills, information and materials; to perform their social roles effectively, and partake in the Saudi local social institutions strongly and effectively, with self-confidence and ability to address the obstacles they face.

Social institutions: voluntary, NGO and nonprofit organizations, made by groups from the community to satisfy the needs and face the problems, whether theirs or others (Al-Murshid, 1999).

Social institution (procedurally): every nonprofit organization or institution or charitable society that aims to provide general services to the members of the Saudi local community, particularly the women. The Saudi women are main partners in them as leaders or active participant members for or without material return, and they seek providing varieties of social material services.

Previous studies: Study of titled: "Inputs of the regional and international NGOs toward the development of the

adults in the developing countries." The study aimed to identify the inputs of the societal institutions that work in adult education field with assistance from the World Bank (WB), which provided materials and experts who helped in enhancing the adult education track. The study employed the descriptive method and questionnaire to obtain the results. It concluded that the WB assisted the social institutions by providing funds, materials, experts and training facilities for the educational courses, whether at the short or long run. It also provided opportunities for all the developing and developed countries to exchange visions, knowledge and views about adult education (Borod, 2011).

Study of titled "Global factors affecting the women's participation in the leadership." It aimed at identifying the factors that hinder or affect the women's participation in leadership through comparison between the cultures and education of the leading women around the world, as well as identifying the powers that help them reach leading positions in the businesses. The results included the following:

- The human and economic development constitutes a basic pivot in the women's advancement. Providing the basic needs such as education, literacy, reproductive health are the most important issues in the states with low women's participation in the leading positions. Meanwhile, health insurance and high education constitute the most important matters in the countries where women have higher rates in assuming leading positions.
- The political and economical freedoms and women's empowerment policies have a large role in increasing the number of the leading women in all aspects.
- Rule of the law, clarity of the property rights, and the state support are essential to facilitate the women's entry to the female activities.
- Women turn to entrepreneurship in countries that provide commercial support, while they tend to join the political activities in the states that do not provide such support.
- The cultural standards that support values of the hard work, personal achievement, readiness to take risk, and participatory leadership are an important indicator of the women's participation in the leading positions (Bullough, 2008).

The study of "Saudi women's empowerment, survey study", aimed at defining the Saudi women's empowerment dimensions and its domains, requirements and levels. The study adopted the descriptive, analytical method, and the data collection was by the study instrument, i.e. the questionnaire. It introduced the following results:

- The most important aspects of the Saudi women's empowerment concept are the process for giving the women chances to obtain their Sharia rights in the community, and enhancing the personal and social power of women to improve their lives.

- The most important domains of Saudi women's empowerment are: educational empowerment, economic empowerment, and obtaining sufficient income to fulfill their needs.

- The most important requirements of the Saudi women's empowerment are qualification needs (education, training) and social needs.

- The most important levels of the Saudi women's empowerment are: the engagement level that relies on achieving positive participation of women in decision-making, capability level that relies on upgrading the women's ability of the objective analysis, and the conscience critic of the discrimination systems between men and women.

Shalhoub (2017) made a study titled "Saudi female human resources toward a strategic framework for a future vision of empowerment." It aimed at reaching schematic indicators of a proposed conceptual framework for a strategy that contributes to the Saudi women's empowerment in the labor market. It displayed the women's personality related self-obstacles that prevent their empowerment in the labor market; and defined the social, cultural and occupational hindrances pertinent to the women's work in the private sector that affect their role in the labor market. The study concluded the following results:

- There are many reasons and obstacles that led to the poor effectiveness of the Saudi women's role in the labor market; some of them are related to the women themselves, such as negative family upbringing in the family surrounding, ignorance of their rights, and low awareness of their developmental role.

- The societal reasons included abstaining professions that include both sexes, preventing them from work with certain families, their interest in the educational jobs only, community low appreciation level of their developmental role, and inferior outlook to some professions created in the community.

- The cultural reasons comprised the community discrimination between the two genders, difficulties that face the women in obtaining leading positions, limited employment opportunities in the private sector, and the stereotype culture, which is that there are roles for women and roles for men.

- The reasons related to the private sector include the women's low wages in this sector as compared with those of the men, lack of information about the available professions and jobs in the private sector, with preference to the foreign labor over the national labor, and limited job opportunities for women.

- The most important indicators of a proposed conceptual framework that aims at women's empowerment are: setting up clear occupational policies that allow the Saudi women actual job opportunities; defining a minimum wage limit in the private sector; decreasing the gap through equality of wages of men and women; linking the female education outputs with the

needs of the public and private sectors' labor market; setting legal measures that preserve the women's work rights in the private sector; and providing and organizing training courses for the women who want to work, to qualify them for the jobs before they join work (Al-Fayiz, 2010).

A study titled "Women empowerment and their role in the development process", which aimed at identifying the dimensions of the qualitative, economic and social empowerment of the working women for wage in the public sector. It further aimed at identifying the relationship between the variables, such as income, years of experience, and occupational degree, and the measurements of the professional, economic and social empowerment of the working women for wages in the official sector. One of the most important results was that working women did not achieve social empowerment on the membership indicator in the civil social institutions and activities, but achieved empowerment in the family decision-taking domain

Thabet (2004) carried out a study titled "Role of the NGOs in empowering the breadwinner women", which aimed at identifying effectiveness of the empowerment strategy in activating the NGOs role with the breadwinner women. The study was carried out on the Community Development Society by the Media, and adopted the empirical method. A prominent result of the study was that there is a statistically significant, positive relationship between activation of the NGOs and empowerment of the breadwinner women.

Abdel Lateef (2005) conducted a study titled "Women and civil societies between marginalization and empowerment: field study in Al-Ghar Village, Sharqia Governorate." The study aimed at describing the reality of the women in the countryside of Zagazig (Egypt), revealing their primary characteristics and economic reality, and describing their role in the political engagement and social and specific awareness. An important result of the study was that the civil community institutions contributed to a wide extent in marginalizing the women in the community in terms of the voluntary works. Even in institutions inside the village, they were marginalized except in certain economic aspects, such as the aids and grants they provide.

Al-Hadi (2003) made a study titled "Reality of the women's empowerment in the Syrian Arab Republic." It aimed at revealing the reality of Syrian women's empowerment politically, economically, and healthily, and comparing this reality with the empowerment areas in the Syrian Arab Republic. The study provided many results, including:

- The engagement of women in the labor force is linked to their traditional roles, i.e. in the agricultural and service works.
- The Syrian women were able to assume the highest positions in the state, such as the Vice President position,

although their contribution in the government and local councils is low.

- The health level of the Syrian women enjoyed large development and wide attention, as the deaths of the mothers and children decreased, and the rate of females who were born under supervision of specialists increased.

- The women's empowerment and development issue is at the top of the Syrian Republic agenda, and is a development priority (Al-Kurdi, 2014).

The researcher recommended placing attention on constructing training programs in empowering the women economically due the high effect of the training in women's empowerment as shown by the results.

Comments on the previous studies

The previous studies have mostly dealt with the importance of empowerment in all the economic, social or scientific empowerment

The current study benefited from the previous studies in:

- Identifying the women's empowerment types, methods of empowerment, particularly the social empowerment.
- Developing the study instrument, its domains and items.
- Adopting the methodology most suitable to the study.

METHOD AND PROCEDURES

Method

The researchers followed the descriptive survey method due to its suitability to the study nature, which enables studying the relationships among the variables, and expresses them quantitatively and qualitatively, leading to conclusions and generalizations that help to explain the studied reality and the prediction with its variables.

Study Population

The study population consisted of all the Saudi women in the community institutions in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Study Sample

The researchers chose a random sample from the different areas of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to be a representative sample for the study, (69) women as per their demographic variables.

Study Instrument

To achieve the study objectives and answer its questions, the researchers constructed its instrument through revisions of the theoretical literature pertinent to the women's empowerment in the social institutions. It comprised three domains that cover the study objectives and questions, namely: empowerment with the women, women's engagement in the local community institutions, and enhancing the women's engagement in the local community institutions. The domains included (24) items in the initial form of the questionnaire.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was presented to a number of professors in the Saudi universities to judge its suitability to the study objectives, language accuracy, and belonging degree of the items to the domain that includes them. Following the approval of the arbiters on its accuracy and deletion of certain items, the questionnaire included (20) items in its final form.

Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, the researchers applied Cronbach Alpha equation on the interviewees' responses using SPSS, and the reliability coefficient factor of the instrument was (0.8261), which is educationally accepted for the study purposes.

Correction and judging criterion on the items, domains and the instrument as a whole

To judge the sample participants' responses, the highest approval rating was given five degrees, and one degree for the lowest rating, with the degrees arranged in a descending order (5, 4, 3, 2, and 1). To identify the responses degrees, the difference between the two limits was divided by 5 levels, by subtracting the maximum limit of the alternatives (5) from the minimum limit of the alternatives (1), which is 4.

Therefore, $4 \div 5 \text{ levels} = 0.8$. Then, when the minimum limit is one degree, then point eight (0.8) is added to every degree according to each item, so that the weights of the items will be as follows:

- (1-1.8): degree with very low mean
- (1.8-2.6): degree with low mean
- (2.61-3.4): degree with medium mean.
- (3.41-4.2): degree with high mean.
- (4.21-5.0): degree with very high mean.

Statistical Processing

To answer the study questions, the researchers entered the raw information into the computer, and the means, standard deviations, frequencies, percentages and χ^2 were obtained.

Presentation and analysis of study data and discussion of its results

This section aims at displaying the results that represented the responses of the study participants to the instrument items, after applying the procedures and analyzing the collected data. Here below are the study results according to the order of the questions:

Results of the first question

What is the degree of Saudi women's empowerment? To know the views of women about their empowerment degree of participation in the social institutes, the researchers calculated the frequencies, percentages, means (Ms), and standard deviations (SDs) of the items, and the results were as illustrated in the following table.

Table (1) shows that Chi square values of all the items were statistically significant at (0.05) level. The results show that there is a convergence in the approvals of the sample participants on the empowerment degree of the Saudi women, as the M's of their approvals ranged between (2.82) and (3.05). The results further showed that the all the items were with medium degree. In this regard, item (4), "Saudi women have suitable experiences and skills that enable them participate in the social institutions", came in the first rank with (3.05) mean. On the other hand, item (8), "Saudi women possess ability to be responsible of the decisions they take", came in the eighth and last rank with (2.82) mean. As for the domain, as a whole, the women's empowerment degree was medium with (2.93) mean. The researcher ascribes this result to that women today are able to acquire knowledge, skills and experiences that make them able to participate in the local community institutions, and leave a prominent role through the availability of the economic and leadership roles that they manage and carry out effectively.

Results of the second question

What is the degree of the Saudi women's engagement in the local community institutions? To identify this degree, the researchers calculated the frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations of the domain items, and the results were as shown in the following table 2.

Table 1. Responses of the sample participants to the items of "Degree of the Saudi women's empowerment" dimension arranged in a descending order as per the agreement means.

No.	Item	Freq.	Agreement Degree				M	SD	Chi ² Value	Sig.	Rank	
			%	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Natural						Agree
4	Saudi women have suitable experiences and skills that enable them participate in the social institutions.	Freq.	-	2	-	25	42	3.05	0.65	10.594	0.01	1
		%	-	29%	-	36.2%	60.9%					
2	Saudi women are seeking training and professional development that help them acquire the required skills that enable them to participate.	Freq.	-	4	7	10	49	3.00	0.80	16.725	0.01	2
		%	-	5.8%	10.1%	14.5%	69.6%					
3	Saudi women participate in the political life which enables them get power to engage in the decision taking.	Freq.	1	3	6	11	48	2.98	0.93	12.667	0.00	3
		%	1.4%	4.3%	8.7%	15.9%	69.6%					
6	Saudi women are empowered of their civil rights that grant them power to defend their rights and participate in the social institutions.	Freq.	1	3	3	17	45	2.96	0.88	12.667	0.00	4
		%	1.4%	4.3%	4.3%	24.6%	65.2%					
5	Saudi women master the use of technology and skills that enable them to participate.	Freq.	5	5	16	7	36	2.93	1.31	16.145	0.00	5
		%	7.2%	7.2%	23.2%	10.1%	52.2%					
1	Saudi women possess ability to deal with crises and manage them in a scientific manner.	Freq.	-	-	2	15	52	2.87	0.51	18.594	0.00	6
		%	-	-	2.9%	21.7%	75.4%					
7	Saudi women possess ability to continue participation despite the critics of others.	Freq.	1	1	6	18	43	2.86	0.83	19.043	0.00	7
		%	1.4%	1.4%	8.79%	61.1%	52.3%					
8	Saudi women possess ability to be responsible of the decisions they take.	Freq.	-	3	3	22	41	2.82	0.98	25.420	0.00	8
		%	-	4.3%	4.3%	31.9%	59.4%					
The domain mean as a whole							2.93	0.72				

Table 2. Responses of the sample participants to the items of "Degree of the Saudi women's engagement in the local community institutions" dimension arranged in a descending order as per the agreement means

No	Item	Freq. %	Agreement Degree				M	SD	Chi ² Value	Sig.	Rank	
			Strongly disagree	Disagree	Natural	Agree						Strongly agree
2	Saudi women take part in framing goals and visions for the social institutions.	Freq. %	- -	1 1.4%	4 5.8%	14 20.3%	50 72.5%	3.00	0.65	19.333	0.00	1
1	Saudi women participate in providing in-kind aids to the charitable societies.	Freq. 5.8%	4 5.8%	6 8.6%	12 17.4%	7 10.1%	40 58.0%	2.92	1,28	6.145	0.04	2
3	Saudi women compete with others in subscribing to the community service institutions as participant members.	Freq. %	0 -	2 2.9%	3 4.3%	12 17.4%	52 75.4%	2.88	0.70	9.319	0.03	3
6	Saudi women focus on being heads of a local, civil, charitable societies.	Freq. %	3 4.3%	6 8.7%	12 17.4%	18 26.1%	30 43.5%	2.87	1.17	23.101	0.00	4
5	Saudi women engage in more than one civil society.	Freq. %	2 2.9%	1 1.49%	15 21.7%	11 15.9%	40 58.0%	2.84	1.03	34.506	0.00	5
4	Saudi women are keen to take part in the voluntary service works.	Freq.	1	4	16	7	41	2.82	1.08	22.32	0.00	6
The Domain as a Whole								2.89	0.72			

Table 2 shows that values of Chi square of all the items were statistically significant at (0.05) level. The results indicate convergence in the approvals of the sample participants on the Saudi women's participation in the local community institutions, and their approvals means ranged between (2.82) and (3.00). The results showed that all the items were in medium degree, and item (2), "Saudi women take part in framing goals and visions for the social institutions", came in the first rank with (3.00) mean. Meanwhile, item (4), "Saudi women are keen to take part in the voluntary service works" was in the sixth and last rank, with (2.82) mean. As for the domain, as a whole, the degree of the Saudi women's participation in the local community institutions was medium with (2.89) mean.

The researchers ascribe this result to the existence of a type of participation in the social institutions, such as partaking in reframing the goals and the visions of the social institutions, and subscribing to the societies. Yet, this participation is still below the desired level that the researchers aspire. Therefore, the researchers recommend making room for women to participate and serve effectively in the social institutions, to fulfill the needs of the community and achieve the social solidarity.

Results of the third question

What is the enhancement level of the participation of Saudi women in local community institutions?

To identify the enhancement level of the participation of Saudi women in local community institutions, the researchers obtained the frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations of the items of the domain, and the results were as indicated in the following table 3. Table 3 clearly shows that Chi square values of all the items were statistically significant at (0.05) level. The results further show convergence among the agreement of the sample participants on the enhancement degree of the Saudi women's participation in the local community institutions. The means of their agreement ranged between (2.90) and (3.08), and the results showed that all the items were with medium level. Item (4), "Women receive material support that increases their self-confidence and empowers them

Table 3. Responses of the sample participants to the items of "Enhancement of the participation of Saudi women's participation the in local community institutions " domain arranged in a descending order as per the approval means

No.	Item	Agreement Degree					M	SD	Chi ² Value	Sig.	Rank
		Freq. %	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Natural	Agree					
4	Women receive material support that increases their self-confidence and empowers them to participate economically.	Freq. 1 % 1.4%	9 13.0%	26 37.7%	22 31.9%	11 15.9%	3.08	0.96	29.768	0.00	1
2	Women receive moral support that increases their self-confidence and empowers them to participate socially.	Freq. 9 -	25 36.2%	23 33.3%	12 17.4%	- -	3.05	0.93	10.942	0.01	2
6	Making the women aware of the importance of their participation and effective role in the societal institutions	Freq. 1 % 1.4%	16 32.2%	24 34.8%	12 17.4%	16 23.2%	3.04	1.13	20.348	0.00	3
1	Making partnerships between the public and private sectors for the societal services where the women are the basic element in them	Freq. 2 % 2.9%	11 15.9%	17 24.6%	20 29.5%	19 27.5%	3.02	1.14	16.145	0.00	4
5	Encouraging women of all segments on subscription in the societal institutions to obtain different types of support.	Freq. 4 % 5.8%	10 14.5%	19 27.5%	23 33.3%	13 18.8%	2.96	1.13	16.145	0.00	5
3	Giving the social institutions wide powers at all levels that allow the women's participation in the social institutions.	Freq. 14 % 20.3%	17 24.6%	25 36.2%	6 8.7%	7 10.1%	2.90	1.20	17.594	0.00	6
General Mean							3.00	0.92			

participate economically", ranked first with (3.08) mean. On the other hand, item (3), "Giving the social institutions wide powers at all levels that allow the women's participation in the social institutions", came sixth and last with (2.90) mean. As for the domain as a whole, the enhancement degree of the Saudi women's participation in the local institutions was medium with (3.00) mean. The researcher attributes this result to the existence of a type of enhancement that highlights the importance of the women's participation in the social institutions. In this concern, there is a type of material and moral enhancement that increases

the women's motivation and desire to participate in the nonprofit social institutions. This is based on the researcher's personal knowledge of increasing the enhancement to encourage the female participation in the societal institutions.

RECOMMENDATION

In the light of the study results, the researchers recommend the following:

- Providing the community awareness of the importance of the women's engagement in the

local social institutions.

- State contributions by offering all the facilities to enable the women participate in the local and international community institutions.
- Spreading out awareness of the women about their social and legal rights in the constitution.
- Activating the women's role and participation in the comprehensive development plans.
- Ensuring the Saudi women's engagement in local and international courses that work to empower them.
- Organizing many training courses to develop

and empower the Saudi women.

- There is a necessity to build programs dedicated to the women's empowerment and integrate them in the public and private sectors, to contribute to the raising of the Saudi women's empowerment degree.
- Developing the education curricula to include the basic subjects that contribute to the Saudi women's empowerment.
- State support for the social institutions that support, and are interested in, the women's empowerment and their participation at the local and international levels.
- Work to eradicate illiteracy in the community, especially among the women, by literacy programs.
- Encouraging the local partnership between the societal and official institutions to support the women's empowerment.

REFERENCES

- Abdel Lateef S (2005). Empowerment and its systems. Higher Institute for Social work, Cairo, Egypt
- Abdel S (2009). Use of empowerment strategy to help the breadwinner women face their problems. *Journal of the Studies in the Social Work and Human sciences*
- Abu Al-Naser (2007). Management of the civil community organizations. Dar Itrack for Publishing and Distribution, Cairo,
- Al-Baghdadi Z (2013). Political, social challenges and their needs in the Council of the Gulf ministries of social affairs: Applied comparison. *Social studies series, No. (71)*, Executive Office of the Ministers of Social Affairs in the Gulf Cooperation Council Member States, Bahrain
- Al-Balawi, Dhaif (2018). Reality of the voluntary work in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The 1st Annual Meeting of the Charitable Institutions, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
- Al-Fayiz M (2010). Saudi female human resources, toward a strategic framework for future vision of empowerment. *Princess Noura Bint Abdel Rahman University*, pp. 558-616
- Al-Hadi, Hamid (2003). Women and the civil societies between marginalization and empowerment: Field study in Al-Ghar Village, Al-Sharqiah. *Globalization and Women Issues and Work*. Printings of Social Research and Studies, Faculty of Arts, Cairo University.
- Al-Haqeel A (2011). Reality of women's practice of their social and intellectual roles in the Saudi community. Unpublished MA Thesis, Naif Arab University for Security Sciences
- Al-Hariri R (2003). Small projects management skills. Egypt, Arab Nile Group
- Al-Jundi, Nadia (2001). Women and development. Symposium on prospects and aspirations of the new century. Public Directorate for Women Affairs, Ministry of Social Affairs and Security, Cairo
- Al-Khalidi N (2013). Women's empowerment in the school curriculum: Analytic study. Dar Al-Manahej for Distribution and Publication, Amman, King Hussein Street, United Insurance Company Building
- Al-Kurdi F (2014). Reality of the women's empowerment in the Syrian Arab Republic. *Tashreen University Journal for Research and Scientific Studies, Arts and human sciences series, V. (36)*, N. (2)
- Al-Maizer H (2015). The Saudi women from marginalization to empowerment in education and work. *Arab Journal for Security Studies, Vol. 32, No. (68)* pp.127-154
- Al-Murshid A (1999). Women's education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia throughout one hundred years (1319-1419 AH). Riyadh, General Presidency for Women Education
- Al-Naimat K (2010). Women's empowerment (Improving Lives in Middle East ANERA), Amman
- Al-Najjar A (2009). Introduction to the economic theory in the Islamic method. Cairo, International Union of Islamic Banks,
- Al-Sa'ati, Samia Hasan (2003). Women's Sociology. Family Bookshop, Egyptian Public Authority Printing Press for Books, Cairo
- Al-Samalouti A (2007). Role of the civil societies in women's empowerment. The 4th Annual Conference: Literacy of the Arab Women: Problems and Solutions. Adult Education Center, Ain Shams University, Dar Al-Fikr Al-Arabi
- Al-Shinnawi, Laila (2006). Policies and programs to reduce poverty. Referential guide of the human development program. Institute of the Agriculture Guidance and Countryside Development Research, Agricultural Research Center, Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation. Egypt
- Al-Sorouji T (2011). Social Capital, Cairo, Anglo Egyptian Bookshop
- Al-Suhaimi, Aref Owaiteeq (2013). Popular participation and women's empowerment in their right of inheritance: descriptive analytical study from the perspective of the public practice in the social work. Egypt, Faculty of Social work, Helwan University
- Al-Yazidi M (2009). Interview with her Highness Princess Sarah Bint Abdel Aziz Al Saud, Thursday, 16/7/1438 AH
- Al-Yousef R (2009). Empowerment of the Saudi women. 1st Ed. Riyadh, Dar Hala for Printing and Publishing
- Borod M (2011). The Input of Regional and International Non-Governmental Organization (NGOs) Towards the Development of Adult Education in Developing Countries *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities* *Vol. 1* *NO. 1*
- Bullough A (2008). Global Factors Affecting Women's Participation in Leadership, Ph.D. Thesis, Florida International University, Florida
- Farah S (2007). Use of Empowerment to develop the marginalized women's abilities in the slum areas. Research published in the 20th International Conference, Faculty of Social Work, Helwan University
- Faraj S (2013). Evaluation of the social security networks in supporting the small size and micro projects to empower poor women. The 24th International Conference for Social work, Helwan University, 4069-4203
- Haddad G (2004). Toward a civil community: Arab civil community and the democratic challenge. Fraidessh Est. Beirut
- Hmoud R (1997). Egyptian women, present problems and future challenges, Dar Al-Amin, Cairo, Egypt.
- Issa N (2004). Civil community: a maneuvering field in the name of the public opinion. Fareed Richard Establishment, Beirut
- Jaleeli Y (2009). Women's empowerment for development. *Development Bridge*, pp.2-8
- Oweis M (2011). The influential relationship between the social and political organizations and achieving the local development. The 12th Annual Scientific Conference. Faculty of Social Work, Cairo University, Part One
- Sa'adallah Y (2009). Empowerment scale of breadwinning women, studies in the social work and human sciences, 18 (4), pp.828-864
- Saeed N (2002). Palestinian women and development. Development Studies Program, Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation. *Planning for Development Series, Third Issue*
- Shalhoub H (2017). Women's empowerment dimensions, survey study as seen by a sample of the Shura Council members and sample of the Faculty members of some Saudi universities. *Arab Journal for Security Studies, V.33, N.(70)* pp.3-70, Riyadh

Thabet N (2004). Women's empowerment and their role in the development process: social study in Cairo. MA Thesis, Faculty of Arts, Ain Shams University, Cairo

UNO (2000). Study about political empowerment of the Bahraini women, as seen by the intellectuals in the Bahraini community: Analytic comparative study. National Council for Women, Cairo, Egypt

Zachariah Al-Dareer (2013). Population and development. Damascus University, UN Fund, Damascus, pp.99-110